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Guidance and Counselling: Panacea for Effective Classroom Delivery among Female Secondary School Students in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper gives a qualitative analysis of guidance and counselling: panacea for effective classroom delivery among female secondary school students in Nigeria. The teaching profession is a profession in which the tutor needs to attain certain level of proficiency or expertise in order to deliver in the classroom effectively. This implies that the classroom holds a very important place in any system of education which needs to be properly managed. The low participation of girls in formal education is a pointer to the fact that a good number of Nigerian women live in a state of extreme deprivation in spite of their need in the area of national development. The paper concludes that despite the impressive goals and objectives of professional educators and educational policy makers, female secondary school students still face hard times and go through a lot of constraints and delivery crisis which militates against their personal development. The paper suggested that more emphasis should be incorporated in the learning and delivery process of teaching by training and retraining of teachers and encouraging teachers to develop their instructional skills and modern teaching practices in order to make them efficient and effective in the classroom. The paper also suggested that counselling services should be offered to both teachers and students which will in turn help manage classroom crisis.

Keyword: Female, Secondary School, Classroom Delivery, Guidance and Counselling and Classroom Instruction.

Introduction

The teaching profession is an art in which the tutor needs to attain certain level of proficiency or expertise in order to deliver in the classroom effectively. This implies that the classroom holds a very important place in any system of education which needs to be properly managed. In modern day Nigeria, the classroom management practices are intended for teachers to provide the necessary supports to make sure students are really learning. But if the teachers lack the ability to control and deliver knowledge to the students it might lead to crisis in classroom which will in turn affect the classroom delivery. Ogunwuyi in Onuma and Nwankwo, (2017) contends that teacher education should be nationally adopted as an agent of change and stability to promote equity and quality as well as serve as a launching pad for sustainable human development. Classroom delivery determines what a person eventually becomes academically. This goes to prove how indispensable the provision of adequate, suitable and child-friendly classroom is for secondary school children to achieve their goals (Nwankwo, Omebe & Anikeze, 2019). This reveals that the classroom occupies a very important place in any system of education. It also implies the need for proper classrooms delivery. Osakwe in Nwankwo, Omebe and Anikeze, (2019) reported that a conducive classroom delivery is needed to promote students' academic achievement in secondary schools. Given the above situation, there is the need for proper management of the available classrooms in secondary schools for quality and sustainability in the system. The molding of a teacher entails the professional training of teachers towards the achievement and improvement of teachers in areas of instructional skills and modern teaching practices which make them efficient and effective in the classroom. From an academic point of view, teaching and learning can only happen in an orderly classroom (Ogbonnia, 2020). The quality of

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classroom delivery will depend on the knowledge, preparation of the lesson and motivation of the teacher which can be influenced positively by the supervisory performance of a school administrator.

In recent times, the widespread poor achievement of students in most subjects taught at the secondary school level in Nigeria have elicited so much attention. While a number of studies have attributed the scenario to student-related factors such as peer influence, study habits, self-esteem, socioeconomic status among others (Ekpoto et al, 2021; Ekpoto et al. 2022); school-related variables such as lack of qualified teachers, conventional teaching methods, conducive classrooms, laboratories as well as, a look at innovative teaching approach might bring about the desired result that appears to have eluded the educational system in Nigeria (Ekpoto, et al. 2022). Classroom instructional strategies employed by a teacher in classroom content delivery could make or mar the expected outcome of teaching-learning no matter how versed he/she might be in the subject concerned. Quite often, most teachers utilise lecture method. Lecture method is a traditional (conventional) chalk-talk method that involves teacher delivery facts, ideas or contents to students (Ezeudu et al 2014; Ekpoto, et al. 2022). It inspires routine memorization and regurgitation of ideas or facts (Ezeudu & Gbendu, 2020; Ekpoto, et al. 2022). Studies have shown that lecture method, although, suitable for large class sizes and quick coverage of curriculum contents, is teacher-dominated and ineffective in attracting students' attitude towards learning (Ezeudu et al, 2014; Abidoye, 2015). To avert the ugly scenario occasioned by the monotonous use of lecture method in secondary school classes in Nigerian schools, there is urgent need for teachers to switch to the use of other innovative teaching styles (Ekpoto, et al. 2022). Universally, education is seen as the mainstay for women development. It is a focal point around which the quick development of economic, political, sociological and human resources of any country is unraveled. The quality of education of any nation determines the development status of that particular nation. The World Conference on education for all in Hakimi, (2017) pointed out that education is a fundamental right of all people, women and men of all ages throughout the world. One of the major issues catching the attention of Nigeria today is that of the education of women and the girl-child. Women play big roles in the development of any nation, be it Nigeria or the Western world. It is common knowledge that the female sex in many countries are the victim of educational inequalities (Adekola & Kumbe, 2016). Education is one important tool often used to measure the development of any nation, through knowledge acquired by members of the society to help them maximize their abilities in our ever-changing world. The need for classroom delivery in the empowerment of the girl child in Nigeria cannot be over emphasized as the basis for Nigeria's development. Egbo (2013) explained that the total development of a child can only take place in an environment suitable for teaching and learning. It is in realization of the above that all educational services which can propel teaching and learning in schools are given prominent attention by educational planners. Counselling services are part of the school educational services. It is believed that guidance and counselling services in school will develop, assess and improve educational programmes; promote teaching and competence.

The education of girls has the ability to bring alive and upgrade traditional skills as well as build confidence in girls in their pursuit for upliftment. Education empowers female secondary school students by improving their quality of life. It is the starting point for women advancement in different fields of human endeavor. It is also the basic tool that should be given to girls in order to fulfill their role as full members of the society. United Nations Funds for Population Activities in Adekola and Kumbe, (2016) observed that more than half of the illiterates in the world are women especially in Africa. United Kingdom Department for International Development (DFID) in Adekola and Kumbe, (2016) also recorded that almost two thirds of the population of the world are females and this accounts for the two thirds of the over one billion people experiencing poverty. It further noted that in the Pacific, Southern Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa 83% girls do not go to school. The New Partnership for African Development [NEPAD] in Adekola and Kumbe, (2016) reported a tragic situation where over 50% of the population of women in Africa are illiterate in the turn of the 21st century when knowledge is of utmost importance. The United Nations Educational, Scientific, Cultural Organization (Adekola & Kumbe, 2016) equally recorded that; girls are 60% of the 300 million children of school age who are not in school.

Classroom Delivery Crisis

According to the 1999 Nigerian constitution section 18 which ensures all citizens irrespective of their race, sex or gender are guaranteed equal rights which reflect the nation's commitments to equality while the national policy of Education in Akinbi and Akinbi, (2015) stipulates that every Nigerian should have a right to equal educational opportunities. The low participation of girls in formal education is a pointer to the fact that a good number of Nigerian women live in a state of extreme deprivation in spite of their need in the area of national development. This has robbed most Nigerian women of the opportunity to contribute fully to national development (Haruna, 2015). If there is crisis or challenges in the classroom delivery among female secondary school students, it will affect the learning outcome of the students, and the intended outcome will not be

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achieved (Akinbi & Akinbi, 2015). Education is largely seen in Nigeria as an indispensable tool which will not only assist in meeting the nation’s social, political, moral, cultural and economic aspirations but will also inculcate in the individual knowledge, skills, dexterity, character and desirable values that will foster national development and self-actualization (Orji and Maekae, 2013). Education is an experience that has a formative impact on the mind, attitude, or physical ability of a person. It is the whole episode of experiences in life through which an individual learns something new through formal, informal and non-formal learning. Classroom delivery has to do with what the teacher does to promote or direct teaching and learning in a particular subject in a school. Classroom delivery entails the act of ensuring that organized teaching and learning is effective in the classroom. This means that the through effective organization of the lesson by preparation of lesson notes, collecting of teaching aids, using of teaching strategies and timely utilization of the equipment to corroborate the teaching are very crucial to the success of classroom delivery. The lack of effective instructional delivery will affect students’ learning experience, subject mastery and performance in the subject being taught (Uthman & Mohammed, 2018). Ayeni in Uthman and Mohammed, (2018) posited that there is a significant relationship between teachers’ qualifications and delivery, and between teachers’ teaching experience and delivery. The study concluded that teachers’ delivery can be enhanced with a good qualification and experience in teaching, while the challenges that teachers experience in the tasks of instructional inputs and curriculum delivery require effective capacity development during service, so as to improve the quality of teaching in secondary schools and the overall quality of the education system.

Female Secondary School Students classroom delivery and National Development

The role of women in the developmental drive of every society calls for their empowerment at all levels. Women in Nigeria are bound to be backward compared to their male counterparts due to marginalization from many areas of life. Roseline, Arikpo and Justin in Yusuf, (2013) opined that educating and empowering the female folk as a way of boosting their capacity to make choices will help in liberating them from poverty and also transform the choices made into desired actions and outcomes. For women to live a better life they need to access opportunities so the need for a successful classroom delivery without crisis cannot be over emphasized. The guidance counsellor also plays a deep role in different areas of their lives such as areas of social awareness, psychological and culturally based counselling, which will enable them have knowledge to transform the world to their advantage. A closer look at the pattern of classroom delivery crisis and female secondary school student’s participation in education in Nigeria reveals abysmal low levels, in spite of all the laudable goals and objectives of education, Nigerian women still face hard time and go through a lot of constraints and inhibitions which militate against their personal and national development from time in memorial (Nzulumike & Oli, 2015). Another challenge that teachers experience is the lack of exposure and limited accessibility to modern instructional facilities. Secondary schools especially in the rural areas do not have access to information communication technology (ICT) which could help improve the shortage of instructional materials. As the world operates as a global village and increase awareness on the use of modern scientific approach in teaching and learning processes in schools (Tety, 2016).

The enrolment of girls in schools and the sustainability of classroom delivery by teachers in Nigeria still need improvement. Some states in Nigeria do better than others in the aspect of girl child school enrolment as well as education delivery to the girl child. The increase and adequate enrolment of rural girls in both primary and secondary schools will help rural communities alleviate poverty as well as foster their development. Primary and Secondary Education Enrolment Available Data from Federal Ministries of Education is Shown in the Table below.

Table 1: Primary and Secondary Education Enrolment Data

Year	2014	2015	2016
Rate of Enrolment of Primary School Age Girls	48.6 %	47.4%	47.5%
Rate of Enrolment of Primary School Age Boys	51.4%	52.6%	52.5%
Rate of Enrolment of Secondary School Age Girls	45.9%	46.5%	46.0%
About 54% of Boys Enrolled in Secondary School Between 2014 - 2015			
Enugu State had the Highest Per cent of Girls Enrolment in Secondary Schools in both 2014 -2015 (55.4%)			
Abia State had the Highest Per cent of Girls in Secondary Schools in 2016			
Kebbi State Recorded the Lowest Per cent of Girls in Secondary School in 2014,2015 and 2016 (29.5%)			

Source: National Bureau of Statistics, 2018.

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Class room delivery and its impact on women in Nigeria can be traced to the coming up of poverty alleviations programmes in the country as a way by which the Nigerian Government boost the economy (Ibharhokanhowa, 2016). If women are not educated then the nation will not grow. Mothers play a big role in the development of any nation. Most of the countries with higher class room delivery attain reasonable development. Poverty elimination strategies became imperative in Nigeria, consequent upon the increasing rate of poverty among Nigerians after the Nigerian independence in 1960. Report has showed that incidence of poverty in Nigeria in 1960 was about 15 percent only but in 1980 it had grown to 28 percent and by 1985 the extent of poverty was about 46 per cent. In 1996, it was noted that poverty incidence in the country was 66 per cent or 76.6 million people from the Nigerian population of 110 million (Ibharhokanhowa, 2016). The availability of infrastructural facility is one of the biggest challenges teachers face as a crisis in classroom delivery in secondary schools in Nigeria. Infrastructural Physical facilities play important role in teaching and learning especially at the secondary school age when the sense of reasoning is still developing (Uthman and Mohammed, 2018). Igbo in Uthman and Mohammed, (2018) discovered that the quality of student learning was related to the quality of classroom instruction. Also, Kinutai and Zachariah in Igbo in Uthman and Mohammed, (2018) discovered that the quality of student learning was related to the quality of classroom instruction. Also, Kinutai and Zachariah in Uthman and Mohammed, (2018) study found positive correlation between the instructional supervision and students' academic performance. The quality of classroom delivery will depend on the knowledge, preparation of the lesson and motivation of the teacher which can be influenced positively by the supervisory performance of the school administrator (Uthman & Mohammed, 2018).

The main concern of government should be the formulation of policies that will encourage human capital development to make students an asset that will drive the economic state of the nation to prosperity (Ekundayo, 2015; Ogbonnaya, 2020). The availability of adequate school building, classrooms, chairs and other facilities are necessary to the attainment of objectives of an educational system. However, the increase in secondary school enrolment does not have corresponding increase in infrastructural development in the secondary schools. A common scene at the secondary school environment is that of half completed or dilapidated and overcrowded classrooms lacking basic equipment and facilities with unsightly and unhygienic toilet. If the enrolment of girls is poor in secondary schools due to inadequate, facilities, lack of trained teachers and other factors it will in turn affect girl's enrolment in secondary schools. Education facilitates is essential for quality learning all through life among people of any age group. It plays an important role in career growth as well as in personal growth of every individual. Thus, effective classroom delivery plus intelligence is the true goal of education (Onwuka, 2014; Ogbonnaya, 2020).

Classroom delivery management practices

Classroom delivery management is a process involving planning, organizing, coordinating, motivating and controlling the actions of learners and materials in order to achieve instructional objectives (Adzongo & Olaitan, 2019). The art of classroom delivery management encompasses all the functions of a classroom teacher in instructional procedure. Such activities include lesson planning and presentation, organization of the classroom facilities, coordination of learning activities, management of instructional materials and leading by example (Nwankwo, 2014; Adzongo & Olaitan, 2019). Classroom management practices also refers to the tactics the teacher employs in the classroom for better teaching and learning (Nwankwo, Omebe & Anikeze, 2019). These tactics of organizing the students in the class include: having better seating arrangements, co-ordinating their activities, monitoring their behaviours, ensuring effective learning process, providing instruction through interactive communication, getting feedback from students, preparing and utilizing instructional materials in facilitating learning, maintaining discipline among learners, evaluating learning outcome, serving as a role model, reinforcing their performance through motivational techniques, giving clear and simple directions, among others. Osakwe (2014) refers to classroom management practices as the tactics or methods adopted by teachers to ensure decorum in the classroom and thus create a healthy and conducive atmosphere for learning. Therefore, classroom managers must be abreast with these effective techniques and practices for effective teaching to take place and quality to be assured in education in Nigeria. The classroom must be arranged properly to accommodate the students, seats and tables, instructional materials and so on. It is also the responsibility of the classroom teacher most especially in secondary schools to make sure that the students are monitored while instruction is on, maintain good teacher/student relationship, communicate effectively for better understanding, and most importantly, make good use of reinforcement to motivate the students for better performance (Nwankwo, Omebe & Anikeze, 2019). For a class room teacher to deliver effectively he/she have to create a safe and effective learning environment for his/her students' quality education. Therefore, teachers should know how to apply strategies that will help students learn (Nwankwo, Mathew & Christiana 2019). Arguing further Zuckerman, in Nwankwo, Mathew and Christiana (2019:107) noted some of these practices as:

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1. Good classroom arrangement. To manage the few facilities provided for students' usage.
2. Use and applying of incentives to motivate students and provide counselling services for those with deviant behaviours.
3. Make rules and regulations that are simple and understandable and be consistent in applying them.
4. Plan the lessons using the scheme of work as a guide, and present lessons from known to unknown facts.
5. Delegate specific responsibilities daily to students and request for regular update and reports from such students.
6. Treat the students' cases justly and equally without bias/partiality-set up a positive behaviour for rewards and punishment system.
7. The teacher should serve as a role model for the students to emulate.

Counselling and Classroom Delivery

Guidance and counselling is a tool that helps in informing children and reforming them and their perception from negative ideas that is planted in them by their peers, the environment they live as well as their experiences. Counselling is a helping process in which a counsellor helps a person learn, understand themselves and their environment and be in a position to choose the appropriate type of behaviours that will help them develop, progress, grow, ascend, mature and step up, educationally, vocationally and socio personally, (Egbo, 2013). Hence there is a need for counsellor to assist the girl child in developing their perception through effective counselling therapies and help them resolve challenges. The school counsellor is expected to be a role model to the students, handle short comings and proffer counselling to students by assisting them to take the most appropriate decisions in life. In counselling, learning through sustainable positive classroom delivery is concern with the assistance given to the individual learner in her educational development and help reduce classroom delivery crisis as well as the development of their social, personal, and career or occupational choice. Akinade in Ebizie and Enajedu, (2016) defines guidance and counselling as a process of helping an individual become fully aware of his/her self and the ways in which he is responding to the influences of his/her environment. The effectiveness of classroom delivery through counselling also plays a big role in reducing the challenges female secondary school students and their teachers face in achieving a fulfilled learning achievement without challenges (Haruna, 2015). The core of the uplifting of the girl child is the ability to use their capabilities and opportunities to expand their wants and ability to control their own destiny (UNU-WIDER, 2014).

Conclusion

The paper concludes that in spite of all the laudable goals and objectives of professional educators and educational policy makers, female secondary school students still face hard time and go through a lot of constraints and delivery crisis which militate against their personal and national development. The paper also concludes that early history of education in Nigeria revealed that woman lacked easy access to formal education. Availability of infrastructural facility is another challenge that teachers and students face in the learning process. It also noted that classroom delivery challenges will affect the learning outcome of the students, and the intended outcome will not be achieved. The paper also concludes that in counselling, learning through sustainable positive classroom delivery is concern with the assistance given to the individual learner in order to help reduce classroom delivery crisis as well as development of their social, personal, and career or occupational choice.

Recommendations

The paper recommends the following:

1. More emphasis should be incorporated in the learning and delivery process of teaching and learning by the training and retraining of teacher and encourage teachers to develop their instructional skills and modern teaching practices in order to make them efficient and effective in the classroom.
2. Adequate infrastructural facilities should be provided to female secondary school students and their teachers in order to facilitate a conducive learning environment.
3. Teachers should build good relationship and communicate effectively for better understanding and most importantly, make good use of reinforcement to motivate the students for better performance which will help in fostering an effective classroom delivery.
4. Guidance counsellors should address female secondary school student's needs, the counselling interventions will help eliminate subtle and complex situation that hinder the learning process.
5. Counselling services should be offered to both teachers and students which will in turn help manage classroom crisis.

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